

Local buckling of cold-formed high-strength steel circular hollow sections Analysis & validation using analytical and numerical approaches

Drilon Gubetini^{*,a}, Martin Mensinger^a

^aTechnical University of Munich, School of Engineering and Design, Chair of Metal Structures, Germany
d.gubetini@tum.de, mensinger@tum.de

ABSTRACT

Cold-formed circular hollow sections (CHS) are becoming more popular for use with higher steel grades and, thus, thinner wall thicknesses. Local buckling as a possible failure mode sets a minimum threshold for the thickness reduction, which, e.g., in EN 1993-1-1, leads to a more conservative cross-section class for high-strength steel than for mild steel. The authors previously conducted stub-column tests on tubes with nominal yield strengths ranging from 355 to 960 MPa and 48.3 and 90.0 mm diameters with different wall thicknesses. These experiments serve as a validation base for numerical analysis of the local buckling behaviour. This article focuses on the finite element modelling approach. Analytical approaches of nonlinear shell theory are initially used to verify the finite element analysis (FEA). Finally, the results obtained from geometrically and materially nonlinear imperfect analyses with different element types are compared with the experimental strains.

Keywords: local buckling, cold-formed, circular hollow sections, high-strength steel

1 INTRODUCTION

The ecologic developments in the steel construction industry, such as CO₂-neutral production ('green steel') and the application of high-strength steel, have positioned steel as a competitive material in the 21st century. Combining these new developments opens a considerable potential for environmentally friendly construction and improved resource efficiency. Structures that require a high payload-to-weight ratio, such as those found in the scaffolding and crane industry, can achieve more slender members. Cold-formed high-strength steel (HSS) circular hollow sections (CHS), typically use thermomechanically rolled steels as coil material. The material is cold-formed into CHS and longitudinally joined, usually through high-frequency induction welding. The local and global stability behaviour of HSS cold-formed CHS under compressive loads requires special attention due to their higher slenderness and different imperfections compared to mild steel. Recent research in the field of high-strength tubular stub columns alludes that current normative regulations may have conservative thresholds for the elastic buckling range (1–3). The D/t ratio in the current draft of EN 1993-1-1 (4) to prevent local buckling (classification as cross-section-class 3) derives as:

$$\frac{d_e}{t} \leq 90 \cdot \varepsilon^2 \quad (1)$$

with d_e Equivalent diameter; corresponds to the outer diameter for CHS
 t thickness
 $\varepsilon = \sqrt{\frac{235}{f_y}}$ with f_y denoting the yield stress (MPa)

Notably, the inverse relationship in Eq. (1) implies lower D/t ratios for higher yield stresses. For HSS, the diminishing influence of structural imperfections, such as residual stresses, on load-bearing

capacity with increasing yield strength opens up possibilities for redefining more economically viable, yet reliable, criteria for HSS CHS design. Therefore, the authors have conducted stub-column tests on cold-formed, high-strength tubular sections commonly used in scaffolding and crane construction and established numerical models. Analytical approaches from shell theory were used for an initial validation before comparison with experimental results. This paper presents the numerical results obtained by the validation process.

2 LOCAL BUCKLING OF TUBES UNDER AXIAL LOADING

Local buckling under pure axial loading can occur due to either a stability problem or a local yielding phenomenon. While the latter describes plastic buckling, the former refers to elastic buckling. Donnell (5) was among the first to derive a reliable theory regarding the critical elastic buckling loads by means of shell-buckling theory with linearized kinematic equations. The theory assumes hinged edge supports with a deformation restraint in the radial and tangential directions.

Fig. 1 Reference system for the derivation of the critical meridional buckling stress for cylinders

Thus, the differential equation system describing the governing equations can be expressed as:

$$K \cdot \Delta \Delta w + t \cdot r \cdot \phi'' + p \cdot r^2 \cdot w'' = 0 \quad (2a)$$

$$\frac{1}{E} \cdot \phi \cdot r \cdot w'' = 0 \quad (2b)$$

with	K	Plate bending stiffness; $K = \frac{Et^3}{12(1-\nu^2)}$
	ν	Poisson-ratio; 0.3 for elastic steel behavior
	w	displacement in local z-direction
	r	radius of the middle surface
	ϕ	Airy's stress function; $\sigma_x = \phi''$, $\sigma_y = \phi''$, $\tau_{xy} = -\phi'$
	E	Young's modulus; 210.000 MPa for steel
and	$(...)'$	derivative with respect to ξ
	$(...)$	derivative with respect to ϕ
	Δ	Laplace operator; $\Delta(...) = \frac{\partial^2(...)}{\partial \xi^2} + \frac{\partial^2(...)}{\partial \phi^2}$

To fulfil the boundary conditions, following approaches are chosen:

$$w = W_{mn} \cdot \sin\left(\frac{m \cdot \pi \cdot r \cdot \xi}{l}\right) \cdot \cos(n \cdot \varphi) \quad (3a)$$

$$\phi = C \cdot \sin\left(\frac{m \cdot \pi \cdot r \cdot \xi}{l}\right) \cdot \cos(n \cdot \varphi) \quad (3b)$$

with m number of half-waves in axial direction (x)
 n number of full-waves in tangential direction (y)
 l length of the cylinder
 W_{mn} amplitude of the peak deformation (indeterminate)
 C free variable

Inserting these approaches in (2a) and (2b) results in a formulation for the critical meridional buckling stress depending on the buckling wave pattern. Thus, the zeros of the differentiation of the equation with respect to m and n results in the minimal buckling stress of a steel cylinder with the given boundary conditions (6):

$$\sigma_{x,cr} = \frac{E}{\sqrt{3 \cdot (1 - \nu^2)}} \cdot \frac{t}{r} = 0.605 \cdot E \cdot \frac{t}{r} \quad (4)$$

The critical stress is primarily of theoretical interest since, due to geometric and structural imperfections, the load capacity of cylindric shells lies well under this value. Moreover, a shortcoming of the applied theory is the consideration of a membrane state only. In reality, the radial deformation restraint violates the membrane theory, thus leading to bending effects (“edge disturbance”). One prominent example is the test setup for stub-column tests, which generally follows the guidelines formulated by Ziemian (7). Flügge addressed and covered this case using nonlinear shell theory (8). The equation system describing this problem is given by:

$$u'' + v \cdot w' - k \cdot w''' = 0 \quad (5a)$$

$$v \cdot u' + w \cdot k \cdot (u''' - w'''' - w) + \frac{P}{D} w'' = 0 \quad (5b)$$

with u axial displacement (x)
 $k = \frac{K}{D \cdot r^2} = \frac{t^2}{12 \cdot r^2}$
 D Plate membrane stiffness; $D = \frac{E \cdot t}{1 - \nu^2}$

The boundary conditions required to solve this system are given in the table below:

Table 1. Boundary conditions for the solution of axially loaded tubes with radial displacement restraint

	Lower edge	Upper edge	For an arbitrary x
(1)	$m_{xx} = D \cdot k \cdot (w'' - u') = 0$	(2) $m_{xx} = D \cdot k \cdot (w'' - u') = 0$	(6) $n_x = \frac{D}{r} \cdot (u' + v \cdot w \cdot k \cdot w'') = -p$
(3)	$w = 0$	(4) $w = 0$	
(5)	$u = 0$		

The solution for the displacement is obtained by two exponential approaches for the axial displacement u and the out-of-plane displacement w , which after the solution of the characteristic polynomial of (5a) and (5b) leads to:

$$u = e^{-\alpha \frac{x}{r}} \cdot \left[A_1 \cdot \cos \left(\beta \cdot \frac{x}{r} \right) + A_2 \cdot \sin \left(\beta \cdot \frac{x}{r} \right) \right] + e^{-\alpha \frac{l-x}{r}} \cdot \left[A_3 \cdot \cos \left(\beta \cdot \frac{l-x}{r} \right) + A_4 \cdot \sin \left(\beta \cdot \frac{l-x}{r} \right) \right] + A_5 + A_6 \cdot \frac{x}{r} \quad (6a)$$

$$w = e^{-\alpha \frac{x}{r}} \cdot \left[C_1 \cdot \cos \left(\beta \cdot \frac{x}{r} \right) + C_2 \cdot \sin \left(\beta \cdot \frac{x}{r} \right) \right] + e^{-\alpha \frac{l-x}{r}} \cdot \left[C_3 \cdot \cos \left(\beta \cdot \frac{l-x}{r} \right) + C_4 \cdot \sin \left(\beta \cdot \frac{l-x}{r} \right) \right] + C_5 + C_6 \cdot \frac{x}{r} \quad (6b)$$

with A_i Integration constants for u

C_i Integration constants for w

In the following, the prerequisite is that $\frac{p^2}{D^2} < 4 \cdot (1-\nu^2) \cdot k$. The values α and β result from the eigenvalues of the characteristic polynomial and, in the given case, are all of complex nature:

$$\lambda_{1,2,3,4} = \pm \sqrt{-\frac{p \cdot r^2}{2 \cdot K} - \nu \pm \frac{l}{2 \cdot k} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{p^2}{D^2} - 4 \cdot (1-\nu^2) \cdot k}} = \pm \alpha \pm i \cdot \beta$$

Inserting (6a) and (6b) in (5a) and (5b) provides a linear relation between the A_i and C_i values. The consideration of the boundary conditions (1) to (4) in Tab. 1 leads to a linear equation system, which enables the solution for the integration constants. The following expresses it as a matrix:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & e^{\frac{\alpha \cdot l}{r}} \cdot \cos \left(\frac{\beta \cdot l}{r} \right) & e^{\frac{\alpha \cdot l}{r}} \cdot \sin \left(\frac{\beta \cdot l}{r} \right) \\ 0 & -1 & e^{\frac{\alpha \cdot l}{r}} \cdot \sin \left(\frac{\beta \cdot l}{r} \right) & -e^{\frac{\alpha \cdot l}{r}} \cdot \cos \left(\frac{\beta \cdot l}{r} \right) \\ e^{\frac{\alpha \cdot l}{r}} \cdot \cos \left(\frac{\beta \cdot l}{r} \right) & e^{\frac{\alpha \cdot l}{r}} \cdot \sin \left(\frac{\beta \cdot l}{r} \right) & 1 & 0 \\ e^{\frac{\alpha \cdot l}{r}} \cdot \sin \left(\frac{\beta \cdot l}{r} \right) & -e^{\frac{\alpha \cdot l}{r}} \cdot \cos \left(\frac{\beta \cdot l}{r} \right) & 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} C_1 \\ C_2 \\ C_3 \\ C_4 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -C_5 \\ C_5 \cdot \left(\frac{\alpha^2 + \beta^2}{2 \cdot \alpha \cdot \beta} - \frac{1-\nu^2}{2 \cdot \nu \cdot \alpha \cdot \beta} \right) \\ -C_5 \\ C_5 \cdot \left(\frac{\alpha^2 + \beta^2}{2 \cdot \alpha \cdot \beta} - \frac{1-\nu^2}{2 \cdot \nu \cdot \alpha \cdot \beta} \right) \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

The constant C_5 results from the sixth boundary condition in Tab. 1 and the consideration of $A_5 = 0$ due to boundary condition (5). The solution describes two superposed out-of-plane displacements starting from each end and decaying rapidly towards the other. Due to the local bending moments arising at the ends, yielding effects due to material nonlinearity will occur and result in an “elephant foot failure”. As this mode arises due to the coupling of geometric and material nonlinearities, it is considered local plastic buckling.

3 COMPARISON OF ANALYTICAL AND NUMERICAL APPROACH

The authors have previously conducted stub-column tests on cold-formed high-strength steel CHS. The coil material (fine-grain structural steel) has undergone a thermomechanical rolling process. The presented approach aims to verify the displacements obtained by numerical models through the following two cases:

Table 2. Parameters of the analysed tubes

nomenclature	diameter d_e [mm]	nominal thickness t [mm]	nominal yield strength f_y [MPa]	length l [mm]	Mean experimental ultimate load P_{Ult} [kN]
48.3-1.8-960	48.3	1.8	960	200	301.1
90.0-2.7-960	90.0	2.7	960	350	739.3

To be able to apply the provided solution of the differential equations, the validity of $\frac{p^2}{D^2} < 4 \cdot (1-\nu^2) \cdot k$ needs to be ensured. Considering a Young's modulus of 210 GPa and a poisson-ratio of 0.3, the following asymptotic upper thresholds P_{res} can be derived:

Table 3. Upper thresholds for the application of the differential equation solution for the presented cases

nomenclature	Cross-section class according to Eq. (1)	D [N/mm]	k [-]	p_{lim} [N/mm]	P_{res} [kN]
48.3-1.8-960	4	415385	$5 \cdot 10^{-3}$	17711	2587
90.0-2.7-960	4	623077	$3.2 \cdot 10^{-3}$	21226	5821

The solution applies to the given cases as the threshold exceeds the experimental ultimate load P_{Ult} . In the next step, a numerical model employing continuum elements (C3D8R) in ABAQUS FEA was established for each tube. Large deflections are accounted for, but analogous to the analytic expression, only elastic material behavior is considered. The subsequent plot illustrates the comparison of the analytic and the FEM approach, assessing the displacement w in the mid-surface.

Fig. 2 a) FE-model with defined reference and support conditions b) deformed system with mesh description c) comparison of the deformations from analytic and FEM-approach for 48.3-1.8-960 and d) 90.0-2.7-960

As depicted in the figure, the FEM approach closely mirrors the analytical approach. Consequently, the selected elements and computational settings demonstrate their validity. An alternative employing shell element was not investigated for this case. Continuum elements were favored over shell elements due to the low wall thickness, where the required element size would align closely with the thickness. This alignment can lead to ill-conditioned behavior in finite element analysis. Additionally, accurately modeling the bending residual stresses resulting from the cold-forming of CHS necessitates the use of two elements across the thickness, as achieved with the C3D8R elements. A linear buckling analysis using four different element types including also shell elements for further verification was conducted to estimate the critical buckling stress given in Eq. (4). The first eigenform and the corresponding critical stress according to Fig. 1 are shown in the next figure:

Fig. 3 Results for eigenform and critical buckling stress using a) S4R: four noded shell element with reduced integration b) C3D8R: 8-node continuum element with reduced integration c) C3D8I: 8- node continuum element with incompatible mode d) C3D20R: 20-node continuum element with quadratic shape functions and reduced integration

The buckling pattern is identical for each element type. However, the C3D8R elements lead to a lower buckling stress than the other elements, which have a reasonable correlation. A correction factor for the critical buckling stress obtained by Eq. (4) needs to be applied due to the warping restraints at the ends. This boundary condition is classified as Yamaki’s condition ‘S1’ (9) or ‘BC1’ according to the DIN 18800 Part 4 (10) and considers a correction factor $\eta=6$ and some terms depending on the length.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sigma_{x,corr} &= \left[1 - \frac{\left(0.4 \cdot \left(\frac{l}{r} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{l}{r} \right)^{0.5} - 0.2 \right)}{\eta} \right] \cdot 0.605 \cdot E \cdot \frac{t}{r} \\
 &= \left[1 - \frac{\left(0.4 \cdot \left(\frac{200}{23.25} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{1.8}{23.25} \right) - 0.2 \right)}{6} \right] \cdot 0.605 \cdot 210,000 \cdot \frac{1.8}{23.25} \\
 &= 8594 \text{ MPa}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{8}$$

As the C3D8R provides the most significant deviation from the analytical solution, in the next chapter, another comparison between a geometric nonlinear calculation of the C3D8R and the most accurate, though computationally expensive, element C3D8I is conducted.

4 VALIDATION OF NUMERICAL RESULTS WITH EXPERIMENTS

As mentioned, the authors conducted stub-column tests on high-strength steel tubes, including those discussed earlier. For the numerical validation presented here, material models established from tensile tests on the same tubes were used as a basis. The geometric imperfections of the tubes, which were milled plane before testing, were analysed using a 3D-Scanner. In cases where an affinity between the eigenmodes obtained from linear buckling analysis and the recorded imperfections was observed, e. g. 48.3-1.8-960, the eigenmode was applied as imperfection pattern, with its maximum measured value as the amplitude, for the sake of simplicity. In other cases, such as 90.0-2.7-960, pseudo-loads triggering the deformation pattern from the measured imperfections were applied. The deformed geometry was then taken as imperfection pattern. For the structural imperfections, residual stresses result mainly from a) uncoiling, b) cold-forming, and c) the subsequent high frequency induction (HFI) welding. While a) is generally neglected due to its minor influence, the cold-forming leads to significant bending residual stresses in both longitudinal and transverse direction along the thickness. The authors have conducted residual stress measurements for the presented tubes using the sectioning method with water jet cutting. The results were described in (11), showing that the main inherent stresses are the bending residual stresses, which appear uniformly along the circumference. If tensile tests on the whole tube have been conducted, the bending residual stresses are already included in the material model. The membrane residual stresses occurring due to the welding process vary along the circumference and thus their local influence on the load-bearing behaviour is not represented in the material model. Thus, they were applied in the FE model using the maximum measured value at the welding seam and the distribution pattern proposed in (3). The stresses are applied only in the longitudinal direction and constant over the thickness. The components of the model with the corresponding residual stresses for 48.3-1.8-960 are shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4 CHS 48.3-1.8-960 a) main model with its components b) residual stresses applied to the model

Since the radial and tangential displacements of the tube strongly impact the load-bearing and deformation behaviour, a realistic approach of the boundary conditions had to be adopted. Contact

behaviour was modelled as the 10 mm deep grooves in the steel adapters had a distance of 0.1 mm to the tube on the outer and inner sides. Normal contact (penetration) was modelled with the ABAQUS option “hard contact”, thus not allowing the transfer of tensile stress across the contact surfaces. The tangential behaviour was modelled with a friction coefficient of $\mu=0.2$ (steel-steel). The adapters themselves are modelled as stiff elements (“discrete rigid elements”) without deformation to portray the contact behaviour. The tubes were modelled using the continuum element types C3D8R and C3D8I. C3D20R and S4R were omitted, since they are not suitable for modelling contact problems. In the weld region, a semicircle with a radius of 0.5 mm was additionally modelled to represent the actual thickness of the corresponding cross-section as realistically as possible. The measured thickness of the test specimens corresponded to 1.87 mm and thus was used as regular thickness in the model. The load in the model is applied in the same manner as in the experiment by a displacement control. Therefore, the top of the tube has a reference point, as shown in Fig. 2, at the top (RP1), which is coupled to the edge surfaces and an incremental increase is preset. The analysis considers both geometric and material nonlinearities in the imperfect system. Two different calculation methods have been examined: the first is the standard simulation option in ABAQUS, “Static General”, referring to a general-purpose analysis option for any problem. The second one, “Static Riks”, is preferable for problems with sensitivities due to geometric nonlinearities and imperfections, which may lead to different paths in the post-buckling regime. Both methods lead to the same result, albeit the authors have seen cases where the results may diverge. An overview of the test-setup, the FE model input and the results at the measurement points (strain gauges & DIC), which are located at the half length, are provided in Fig. 5:

Fig. 5 Overview over the test-setup, the implemented material law and the derived geometric imperfection and comparison of the numerical and experimental load-strain curves

The experimental and numerical data show minor deviations when approaching the maximum load, which might be explained by the simplification of the eigenform as imperfection. The comparison of the results in Fig. 5, which were obtained using element type C3D8R, with C3D8I showed good accordance until the pre-buckling regime. As C3D8R tends to be less stiff in bending, the ultimate point and the post-buckling regime for C3D8I occur later due to delayed yielding, and thus, the load-increment path is slightly shifted to the right (cf. Fig. 6).

Fig. 6 Comparison of the load-increment curves for 48.3-1.8-960 using different element types

For 90.0-2.7-960, only tensile tests on coupons were performed. As previously conducted tests on both tubes and coupons revealed lower yield- and tensile strengths for the coupons, the FE-Analysis was expected not to show a representative component behaviour. Consequently, yield strength and tensile strength were obtained for the material derivation by amplifying the tensile and yield strengths from the coupon tests with an amplification factor derived from the tests on 48.3-1.8-960. A trilinear material law was implemented, where the first kink represents the yield stress and the second one is the tensile strength with a slight slope for numerical stability. In addition to the membrane residual stresses, the bending residual stresses were modelled as a predefined stress field with a tension-compression pair in circumferential and longitudinal direction. The bending residual stress in the circumferential direction results to $\sigma_{b,c} = \pm 1.0 \cdot f_y$ and due to the plastic Poisson-effect $\sigma_{b,l} = \pm 0.5 \cdot f_y$. Thus, the gradual yielding behaviour usually present in cold-formed CHS attributed to the inherent bending residual stresses is represented. The recorded imperfection did not match any of the first five eigenmodes, so a pseudo load was generated to obtain a similar pattern. A summary of the FE model input is given in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7 Implemented material law, derived geometric imperfection and comparison of the numerical and experimental load-strain curves for 90.0-2.7-960

The chosen approach accurately portrays both the stress-strain behaviour and the failure mode. As for the 48.3-1.8-960, the comparison with the C3D8I leads to a consistent load-increment path in the pre-buckling regime. Despite the affinity in the load-increment pattern, the ultimate load here was 2.7% higher than for the C3D8R elements. In both cases from Tab. 4, the failure mode manifested as an elephant-foot in the plastic regime, as evidenced by the load-strain graphs. A local elastic buckling was not observed, despite both tubes being categorized cross section class 4 according to Eq. (1).

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